

Accurate Electrical Modeling of Bifacial Photovoltaic Modules

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Abstract—Bifacial Photovoltaic (PV) are the trend in the solar market. However, their electrical modeling is under-investigated in the literature. Typically, the contribution from the rear is modeled as a linear addition in the photogenerated current, while the remaining Single-Diode-Model (SDM) parameters are assumed to be the same as in monofacial operation. Recent research has already challenged this simplistic approach. This study aims to provide an electrical model that accurately predicts the performance of bifacial PV modules. First, a comprehensive investigation of the Single Diode Model (SDM) is conducted for each of the three modes of operation: front-only, rear-only, and bifacial. The results align with recent studies, showing error percentages that can go as high as 15% for bifacial modeling and 30% for rear modeling, particularly within the exponential region of the I-V curve. To address these deviations, an enhanced circuit model enhanced circuit model is proposed. This model extends the SDM by incorporating an additional diode-resistance branch designed to capture rear-side recombinations and extending to bifacial operation. A modified Two-Step Linear Least Squares (TSLLS) method is developed to extract its parameters. The proposed model was validated against the Double Diode Model (DDM), showing superior accuracy and more uniform error distributions, effectively decreasing the overall bifacial error to $< 8\%$ and the rear error to $< 12\%$. The results are validated using outdoor I-V measurements under various albedo surfaces, tilt angles, and meteorological conditions.

Index Terms—Bifacial PV, Electrical Model, Single Diode Model (SDM), Modified Two Step Linear Least Squares (TSLLS).

I. INTRODUCTION

BIFACIAL PV cells have been developed to increase the efficiency of solar systems by generating electricity from both sides [1]. Under optimal conditions, rear-side generation can boost the energy production of bifacial PV systems by up to 10% – 30% [2]. Half-cut panels are another PV technology designed to reduce losses and improve the shade-tolerance of PV systems [3]. The combination of Half and bifacial PV is becoming a dominant trend in the solar market [4].

In most studies, bifacial modules are modeled using the Single Diode Model (SDM) or, less frequently, the Double Diode Model (DDM). In this model, the photogenerated current is assumed to be a linear sum of the photogenerated currents from the front and rear and the remaining SDM parameters are considered to be identical to those of monofacial operation [1], [5]–[12]. However, it was shown in [13] that this assumption leads to errors that can exceed 15%. Such errors may impact the findings of research relying on this model, particularly for

yield predictions and the determination of optimal installation conditions. Other studies treat the front and rear sides of the bifacial panel as two independent monofacial panels connected in parallel, with each side represented by its own SDM [12], [14], [15]. However, a comparison conducted in [16] demonstrated that this approach results in even higher errors than the previous model. According to [16], SDM leads to the lowest error of 20% at worst. The authors in [13], [17], [18] proposed rescaling of the SDM parameters to represent bifacial operation. In [17], [18], corrections were introduced on the series resistance R_s only. As a result, although not explicitly stated, it can be inferred that these works attribute the error to the exponential region of the I-V curve; an inference supported by the findings of this research. In contrast, the authors in [13] attributed the mismatch to the linear summation of the front and rear currents. They argued that the bifacial photocurrent is reduced due to overlapping collection probability in common areas between the front and the rear inside the module. They introduced a correction factor to account for this reduction. Additionally, they reformulated the remaining parameters to incorporate contributions from both front and rear SDMs.

In brief, the widely accepted electrical model of bifacial PV panels is proven to be insufficiently accurate, and the few existing models in the literature lack consensus. Therefore, deeper evaluations are necessary to understand the root cause of their discrepancies and to develop more reliable models capable of representing each one of the three modes of operation accurately, including the rear. Additionally, the previous studies, except [13], were validated using indoor measurements at STC conditions only [16]–[18]. To address these limitations, first, the classic SDM for the three modes of operation is thoroughly analyzed. The I-V curves are obtained using outdoor measurements of a half-cut bifacial panel (Renogy RSP220DT [19]). To the best of our knowledge, there aren't any studies that validate bifacial models using data from half-cut bifacial PV cells, despite their growing adoption in the solar market. Therefore, this work contributes to the literature by including this technology. Notably, the rear exhibit systematically unusual diode parameters, suggesting that the SDM in its lumped form fails to capture. To account for these limitations, a parallel branch of diode-resistance is added to the rear SDM. Subsequently, a modified Two-Step Linear Least Squares (TSLLS) method [20] is developed to handle the increased mathematical complexity of the proposed rear model, whose parameters cannot be directly solved using the traditional TSLLS. Finally, the relationships between front, rear, and bifacial parameters are derived. The contributions of this study are the following:

- 1) It provides insights into the electrical modeling of bifacial modules and how the front and rear interact together during

Manuscript received: XXX

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bifacial operation.

- 2) It proposes an accurate electrical model for rear-only operation, a mode that is usually neglected. This is important in cases where the front might be fully covered, such as in regions with heavy snowfall. It can serve as a foundation for more accurate yield predictions of bifacial systems.
- 3) It develops a modified TSLLS method to extract the parameters of the proposed model.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the single diode PV model is examined in section II. The proposed model is developed in section III. Section IV explains how bifacial I-V can be reconstructed using front and rear models. Finally, conclusions and future works are discussed in section V.

II. CLASSIC SINGLE/DOUBLE DIODE MODEL OF BIFACIAL PV

The Single Diode Model (SDM) is the predominant electrical model of PV systems [13]. The second most predominant is the Double Diode Model (DDM). The conventional SDM and DDM of bifacial PV modules are illustrated in Fig. 1. In these models, the bifacial photogenerated current I_{ph_B} is a linear summation of the photogenerated current by the front I_{ph_f} and the rear I_{ph_r} . It is usually expressed as [1]:

$$I_{ph_B} = I_{ph_f} + I_{ph_r} \quad (1)$$

The rear structure is typically less optimized than the front. Therefore, for the same irradiance, the rear generates less current [5]. The bifaciality coefficient \mathcal{B} is a measure of front-to-rear performance ratio, and it is given by:

$$\mathcal{B} = \frac{I_{sc_r}}{I_{sc_f}} \quad (2)$$

Where $I_{sc_{f,r}}$ are the front and rear short circuit currents measured at the same conditions independently [7]. Subsequently:

$$I_{ph_B} = I_{ph_f} \left(1 + \mathcal{B} \frac{G_r}{G_f} \right) \quad (3)$$

$G_{f,r}$ are the front and rear irradiances. The remaining parameters of the SDM are: the diode $D1$ represents the behavior of the p-n junction of the cell and is responsible for the non-linear characteristics of the I-V curve; the parallel resistance R_p accounts for leakage current through alternate paths within the cell; and the series resistance R_s is the Ohmic resistance between the semiconductor and metal contacts. The DDM adds another diode $D2$ to represent the recombination mechanisms uncaptured by $D1$. The DDM improves the accuracy but increases the complexity of the model [1], [21]. The I-V relationship is expressed as:

$$I = N_p I_{ph_B} - I_{D1} - I_{D2} - N_p \frac{\frac{V}{N_s} + \frac{I R_s}{N_p}}{R_p} \quad (4)$$

N_s is the number of cells in series strings, N_p is the number of parallel strings. I_{D1} and I_{D2} are given by Shockley equation:

$$\begin{cases} I_{D1} = N_p I_{s1} \left(e^{\frac{\frac{V}{N_s} + \frac{I R_s}{N_p}}{a_1 V_t}} - 1 \right) \\ I_{D2} = N_p I_{s2} \left(e^{\frac{\frac{V}{N_s} + \frac{I R_s}{N_p}}{a_2 V_t}} - 1 \right) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. Single and Double Diode Model of Bifacial PV Modules.

Where I_{s1} , I_{s2} are the reverse saturation currents ($I_{s2} = 0$ in SDM), and a_1 , a_2 are the diodes' ideality factors, usually between 1 and 2. $V_t = kT/q$ is the thermal voltage where T is the cell temperature in Kelvin, q is the electron charge ($1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} C$), and k Boltzmann's constant ($1.38 \cdot 10^{-23} J/K$).

Modeling bifacial PV by incorporating an additional current source to the traditional SDM or DDM to represent the rear-side contribution is simple and convenient, especially since most manufacturers of bifacial PV only provide monofacial performance in their Datasheets. On the other hand, the remaining parameters are assumed to be identical to the monofacial mode, and any effects or interactions between the front and the rear are ignored [1], [13], [18]. Moreover, there is an ambiguity when it comes to modeling the rear. The model suggests that in the case of rear-only mode of operation, the photocurrent of the front is deactivated while the rest of the parameters remain the same. This assumption will be proven inadequate for rear modeling.

A. Experimental Setup

Outdoor measurements of the IV-curves of Renogy RSP220DT-G1 PV Panel [19] were taken using HT Instruments I-V400W IV tracer in the backyard of Lucien-Brault, University of Quebec en Outaouais (UQO) J8Y 3G5, Québec, Canada. The measurements include three real-field bifacial operation modes: front-only with the rear covered, rear-only with the front covered, and bifacial mode. The cover is fully opaque on one side and highly reflective on the other to block any light transmission. The measurements were taken under different tilt angles: 30° , 45° , 60° , and 90° on surfaces with different albedo: grass, concrete, and a white sheet. To maximize rear irradiance uniformity, the panel was positioned to eliminate partial self-shading and ensure the support and wires didn't obscure the rear. The tests encompass a wide range of meteorological conditions, with front irradiance ranging from 400 – $1090 W/m^2$, rear irradiance from 50 – $200 W/m^2$, and temperatures between 20 – $58 C^\circ$. The experimental setups are shown in Fig. 2

B. Results and Discussion

The SDM parameters were extracted for each test using the Two-Step Linear Least Squares Method (TSLLS) proposed in [20] and available online in [22]. The authors in [13] used this online tool to extract their SDM parameters. In this study, the algorithm was implemented in MATLAB environment. TSLLS has gained popularity thanks to its accuracy, speed, and

Fig. 2. Experimental setups

simplicity. Additionally, unlike the metaheuristic optimization techniques used in [17], [18], no initializations are required, and the extracted parameters don't vary across repeated iterations.

1) *SDM of bifacial modes*: This part evaluates front, rear, and bifacial properties under the traditional bifacial setup in Benchmark 2: front facing the sun and rear facing the ground. To account for irradiance and temperature variations between the tests, albeit minimal, translations were performed using the following set of equations [16], [23]:

$$\begin{cases} I_{ph} = I_{ph_{ref}} \frac{G}{G_{ref}} [1 - \alpha(T - T_{ref})] \\ R_s = R_{s_{ref}} \\ R_p = R_{p_{ref}} \left(\frac{G_{ref}}{G} \right) \\ a = a_{ref} \\ I_s = I_{s_{ref}} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 e^{\frac{qE_g}{N_s n k} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T} \right)} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where $\alpha = 0.06\%$ is the current temperature coefficient provided in the datasheet [19]. The parameters of front and rear SDMs were adjusted to match bifacial conditions. The effective bifacial irradiance G_B is defined as [18]:

$$G_B = G_{B_f} + \beta G_{B_r} \quad (7)$$

$G_{B_{f,r}}$ are the front and rear irradiances the panel received during bifacial operation. The resulting parameters are presented in Fig. 3. It is important to note that the irradiance and temperature values are not presented sequentially, i.e., an increase in irradiance isn't necessarily met with an increase in temperature and vice versa. The photogenerated current, series resistance, and parallel resistance are sorted with respect to the irradiance, whereas the ideality factor and saturation current are sorted with respect to the temperature.

Fig. 3(a) shows the bifacial photocurrent together with the sum of the front and rear photocurrents, each translated to their respective bifacial irradiances G_{B_f} and G_{B_r} , respectively. The superposition of front and rear photocurrent matches the measured bifacial photocurrent closely with no signs of the overlapping effects reported in [13]. Fig. 3(b) presents the series resistance. The rear $R_{s_{rB}}$ values fluctuate strongly and lack consistency, while the front and bifacial values remain stable around an average of $43m\Omega$. Fig. 3(c) illustrates the parallel resistance. The front and rear parallel resistances are translated to the effective bifacial irradiance G_B . The trend suggests that the bifacial R_{p_B} is functionally related to the front $R_{p_{fB}}$ and rear $R_{p_{rB}}$. Figs. 3(c)-(d) depict the ideality factor and the saturation current. The front and the bifacial

mode are comparable, with an average ideality factor of 1.12, and logarithmic saturation currents of -20 for front and -19.3 for bifacial mode. By contrast, the rear shows low saturation currents and ideality factor below unity. In real-field conditions, a ground-facing rear is expected to experience some anomalies due to reduced and non-uniform irradiance, however, similar low rear-diode parameters have also been reported under laboratory-controlled STC measurements in [13].

2) *Rear and Bifacial Reconstruction using front-SDM*: This section evaluates the accuracy of the traditional bifacial model (front-based SDM with an added rear photocurrent source) in representing both rear-only and bifacial modes. The I-V curves were reconstructed by substituting the photocurrent with the corresponding photocurrent for rear-mode, and the sum of the front and rear photocurrent for bifacial mode. The remaining front-SDM parameters were kept unchanged, only translated to the respective rear or bifacial meteorological conditions. Fig. 4 shows some measured versus reconstructed I-V curves for different irradiance and temperature conditions. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), as well as the Maximum Power Error (ΔP) in percentages % are recorded in Fig. 5. A common mismatch in the exponential region of the I-V curves is observed for both rear and bifacial modes, particularly for the rear, whose MAE and RMSE can go as high as 20% – 30%, respectively. Notably, the rear-IV curves do not exhibit staircase structures often attributed to non-uniform irradiance mismatch. Instead, their morphology appears squarer than the front, with sharper knee transition to V_{oc} . The bifacial MAE and RMSE are lower than the rear but still substantial, reaching up as high as 15% – 20%. The maximum power is overestimated in both cases, ΔP is between 10% – 20% for the rear and can reach up to 5% for the bifacial operation. These results prove that the classic front-based SDM is inaccurate for modeling bifacial operation, all the more the rear operation. Additionally, the error is concentrated around the exponential region, which also substantiates the mismatch in a_r , and I_{sr} of the previous section.

To recapitulate, the results in this section show: 1) the validity of the hypothesis that the bifacial photogenerated current is a linear summation of the front and rear; 2) the failure of the classical bifacial SDM based on monofacial parameters to accurately adapt to all three modes of operation, particularly the rear; 3) The error of the classical bifacial SDM model is mainly concentrated around the exponential region; 4) The rear SDM parameters exhibit great deviations in recombination parameters. Results from other studies that are in agreement with these findings are: a) in [13], similarly low saturation current and ideality factor values below unity were reported for the rear under indoor measurements; b) in [16], the authors reported square I-V curves similar to the observed rear I-V characteristics, emphasizing particular sensitivity of the saturation current to the model accuracy.

III. DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROPOSED REAR MODEL

The preceding analysis demonstrates that the rear-side I-V characteristics exhibit a systematic deviation from the assump-

Fig. 3. Extracted SDM parameters of front-only, rear-only, and combined bifacial modes and their boxplots

Fig. 4. Rear and bifacial I-V curve reconstruction using the classical SDM

Fig. 5. RMSE, MAE, and ΔP of Reconstructed rear and bifacial IV-curves using front-based SDM

tions underlying the lumped SDM, most notably an extended quasi-linear region and a delayed onset of exponential current decay from I_{sc} toward V_{oc} . As shown in Section II, this behavior cannot be reproduced without either introducing unphysical parameter values or accepting fitting errors in the knee region. A natural extension of the SDM is the DDM, which introduces a second recombination mechanism. However, its conventional formulation, where both diodes are connected directly in parallel, does not provide an additional degree of freedom to delay the onset of exponential conduction. Instead, increasing

recombination through a parallel diode tends to soften the knee, which is opposite to the experimentally observed rear-side behavior. Moreover, for bifacial devices, the front and rear share the same p-n junction and contact network; consequently, treating the two sides as electrically independent diode systems has been shown to degrade modeling accuracy rather than improve it [16].

Instead of introducing additional recombination strength, the experimental evidence points to a 'delayed activation' of an additional exponential current contribution at higher voltages. This delayed recombination mechanism can be modeled using a parallel branch that contains a resistance R_h in series with a diode D_h placed in parallel with the main SDM branch, and whose ideality factor and saturation current are denoted a_h and I_h , respectively. This branch is described in [24] but is rarely utilized in the literature. The series resistance R_h reduces the voltage seen by the diode D_h , thereby delaying its turn-on to higher voltages. This directly reproduces the extended linear region and sharp knee observed in the rear I-V curves without distorting the primary diode parameters.

The proposed model of the rear totaling 8 electrical parameters is illustrated in Fig.6. Using Kirchhoff's law, the rear current expression can be determined:

$$I = N_p I_{ph_r} - I_D - I_H - \frac{N_p}{N_s} \frac{V_D}{R_{p_r}} \quad (8)$$

Where:

$$\begin{cases} V_D = V + I R_s \frac{N_s}{N_p} \\ I_D = N_p I_s \left(e^{\frac{V_D}{a V_t}} - 1 \right) \\ I_H = N_p I_h \left(e^{\frac{V_D - I_H R_h}{a_h V_t}} - 1 \right) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Since the bifacial PV is one physical cell, the front and the rear must have coupled losses. The previous results demonstrated that the front and bifacial modes have the same series resistance $R_{sf} = R_{sB} = R_s$, and comparable ideality factor $a_f = a_B = a$, and saturation current $I_{sf} = I_{sB} = I_s$. Those parameters are assumed to be shared by the rear as well. Hence, V_D and I_D become known terms. Let $I' = I + I_D$, so Eq. (8) can be rewritten as:

$$I' = N_p I_{ph_r} + N_p I_h - N_p I_h \left(e^{\frac{V_D - I_H R_h}{a_h V_t}} \right) - \frac{N_p}{N_s} \frac{V_D}{R_{p_r}} \quad (10)$$

Finally, the optimization variables that need to be determined for the proposed model are reduced to five: 1) the

Fig. 6. The proposed electrical model of rear operation

photocurrent I_{phr} ; 2) the parallel resistance R_{pr} ; 3) the inhomogeneous resistance R_h ; 4) ideality factor a_h ; and 5) the diode's D_h saturation current I_h .

A. Parameter Extraction using a Modified TSLLS method

TSLLS treats the current to be fitted (in this case, "I'") as the superposition of a linear term and an exponential term. Rearranging Eq. (10) yields:

$$I' = A - BC^{V_D} D^{-I_H} - EV_D \quad (11)$$

Where:

$$\begin{cases} A = N_p I_{phr} + N_p I_h \\ B = N_p I_h \\ C = e^{\frac{1}{N_s a_h V_t}} \\ D = e^{\frac{R_h}{N_s a_h V_t}} \\ E = \frac{N_p}{N_s R_p} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

From Eq. (11) the linear I_{lin} and the exponential I_{exp} terms are deduced:

$$\begin{cases} I_{lin} = A - EV_D \\ I_{exp} = -BC^{V_D} D^{-I_H} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

First, the linear components A and E are extracted by assuming that the exponential effect is negligible for a set of points 1 to L . So, $I' \approx I_{lin}$. Rewriting I' for a set of points (V_{D1}, I'_1) to (V_{DL}, I'_L) :

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -V_{D1} \\ 1 & -V_{D2} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & -V_{DL} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A \\ E \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} I'_1 \\ I'_2 \\ \vdots \\ I'_L \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Eq. (14) is a well-known linear least squares problem to which the solution is in the form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A \\ E \end{bmatrix} = (\Phi_L^T \Phi_L)^{-1} \Phi_L^T \begin{bmatrix} I'_1 \\ I'_2 \\ \vdots \\ I'_L \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Where:

$$\Phi_L = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -V_{D1} \\ 1 & -V_{D2} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & -V_{DL} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Φ_L^T is the matrix transpose of Φ_L .

Second, the exponential parameters in the traditional TSLLS are obtained by taking the logarithm of Eq. (11). However, this is not possible for this model because a variable term I_H is present in the exponent. A modified TSLLS method is developed to work around this problem. Let X be defined as:

$$X = A - EV_D - I' \quad (17)$$

From Eqs. (10)-(11):

$$I_H = X - N_p I_h = X - B \quad (18)$$

Substituting Eq. (18) in Eq. (17)

$$X = (BD^B) C^{V_D} D^{-X} \quad (19)$$

Taking the logarithm of Eq. (19):

$$\ln(X) = \ln(BD^B) + \ln(C)V_D - \ln(D)X \quad (20)$$

Rewriting Eq. (20) for a set of points $N - M$, where N is the point that corresponds to the open circuit voltage:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{DN-M} & -X_{N-M} & 1 \\ V_{DN-M+1} & -X_{N-M+1} & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ V_{DN} & -X_{N-M} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ln(C) \\ \ln(D) \\ \ln(BD^B) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \ln(X_{N-M}) \\ \ln(X_{N-M+1}) \\ \vdots \\ \ln(X_N) \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

So, using linear least squares a second time:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \ln(C) \\ \ln(D) \\ \ln(BD^B) \end{bmatrix} = (\Phi_E^T \Phi_E)^{-1} \Phi_E^T \begin{bmatrix} \ln(X_{N-M}) \\ \ln(X_{N-M+1}) \\ \vdots \\ \ln(X_N) \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

Where:

$$\Phi_E = \begin{bmatrix} V_{DN-M} & -X_{N-M} & 1 \\ V_{DN-M+1} & -X_{N-M+1} & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ V_{DN} & -X_{N-M} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

L is increased from 2 to N and for each value of L , the algorithm is executed for incremental values of M from 3 to $N - 1$. For each iteration, the parameters (A, B, C, D, E) are calculated. The PV current and the RMSE are calculated using a nested Newton-Raphson method. If the RMSE of the current iteration is smaller than the previous, the parameters are saved as the new optimum, and so forth until all combinations of L and M are executed. Finally, the original parameters $(I_{phr}, R_{pr}, R_h, a_h, I_h)$ are deduced from the optimal (A, B, C, D, E) using Eq. (24):

$$\begin{cases} I_{phr} = \frac{1}{N_p} \left(A - \frac{W(\ln(D)e^{\ln(BD^B)})}{\ln(D)} \right) \\ R_{pr} = \frac{N_p}{N_s} \frac{1}{E} \\ R_h = \frac{N_p}{N_s} \frac{\ln(D)}{\ln(C)} \\ a_h = \frac{1}{N_s V_t} \frac{1}{\ln(C)} \\ I_h = \frac{1}{N_p} \frac{W(\ln(D)e^{\ln(BD^B)})}{\ln(D)} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

Where W is the lambert function defined by $W(x)e^{W(x)} = x$. It is noted that the DDM is a special case of the proposed

Fig. 7. Reconstructed rear IV-curves using DDM and the proposed model

model and can be established by simply setting $R_h = 0$. In that case, the model automatically simplifies to DDM as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \ln(BD^B)|_{D=1} = \ln(B) \\ I_{h|\ln(D) \rightarrow 1} = \frac{W(\ln(D)e^{\ln(BD^B)})}{\ln(D)} = \frac{1}{N_p} e^{\ln(B)} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

B. Results and discussion

The proposed model was implemented in MATLAB. The DDM was also implemented to distinguish it from the proposed model. The ideality factor was forced to values between 1 and 2. Some reconstructed IV-curves using DDM and the proposed model are depicted in Fig. 7. The errors of the total samples, sorted in decreasing order with temperature, are shown in Fig. 8. The reconstructed currents fit the measured I-V curves significantly better than the classic SDM shown in Fig. 4. The proposed model achieves lower errors than the DDM at higher temperatures (left side of Fig. 8), whereas at lower temperatures (right side of Fig. 8) the DDM is slightly more accurate. For the DDM, the error remains relatively uniform, with an MAE of 3% – 6%, RMSE \approx 4% – 9%, and $\Delta P < 9\%$. At higher temperatures, the proposed model reduces the errors further to MAE $< 4\%$, RMSE \approx 3% – 5%, and $\Delta P < 4\%$. This confirms the superiority of the proposed model, especially near the knee region (lower ΔP). However, at lower temperatures, the error of the proposed model increases to MAE $\approx 4\% - 7\%$, RMSE $\approx 5\% - 11\%$, and $|\Delta P| < 6\%$. The increased error might be attributed to reduced recombinations at lower temperatures, producing an abrupt "vertical" exponential drop. This behavior differs from "delayed exponential". The proposed model, in attempting to accurately fit the knee, delays the exponential drop, and therefore it slightly stretches V_{oc} , which increases the error at lower temperatures.

IV. PROPOSED BIFACIAL PV MODEL

In this section, the previous rear model will be combined with the front model to construct the bifacial model. The proposed bifacial model is depicted in Fig. 9, it incorporates the three modes of operation simultaneously and can easily adapt from one mode to the other as it can be seen in Figs. 9(a)-(c). The breakdown of the proposed model's parameters is as follows:

- Photocurrent I_{ph} :** the model adopts the traditional sum of the photocurrents generated by the front and the rear. The

 Fig. 8. RMSE, MAE, and ΔP of rear IV-curves fitted using the DDM and the Proposed Model

expression of the bifacial photocurrent in the proposed model is:

$$I_{phB} = I_{phf} + I_{phr} \quad (26)$$

- Series Resistance R_s :** the series resistance is assumed constant and similar among the three modes of operation. Notably, the value of R_s must be extracted from either monofacial or bifacial measurements and cannot be obtained from rear-only measurements. R_s is given by:

$$R_{sB} = R_{sf} = R_{sr} = R_s \quad (27)$$

- Parallel Resistance R_p :** The bifacial parallel resistance R_{pB} is considered to be the effective resistance of the individual front resistance R_{pf} and rear resistance R_{pr} connected in parallel. The parallel resistance is calculated as follows:

$$R_{pB} = R_{pf} || R_{pr'} \quad (28)$$

Where R_{pf} and $R_{pr'}$ are the measured parallel resistances of the front and the rear translated to the operating conditions of bifacial modes. Unlike Eq. (6) which suggests that the translation is performed with respect to effective bifacial irradiance G_B , the translations of the parallel resistances are performed with respect to the separate irradiances received by the panel during bifacial operation: G_{Bf} and G_{Br} . That is:

$$\begin{cases} R_{pf'} = R_{pf} \frac{G_f}{G_{Bf}} \\ R_{pr'} = R_{pr} \frac{G_r}{G_{Br}} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

To represent each mode alone, the parallel resistance of the other mode is deactivated. For example, to model monofacial mode, R_{pr} must be deactivated. In Eq. (29), monofacial mode means $G_{Br} = 0$ and $R_{pr'} = \infty$ (open circuit), which means R_{pr} is automatically deactivated. Similarly, to model rear-only mode, $G_{Bf} = 0$ and R_{pf} gets deactivated.

Fig. 9. The proposed Bifacial PV model: a) bifacial mode; b) front-only (monofacial) mode; c) rear-only mode

- d) *Ideality Factor a* : The recombination losses represented by the single-diode are assumed to be shared by three modes of operation. Therefore, the ideality factor a is the same among them. Just like the series resistance R_s , a must be measured from either monofacial or bifacial measurements. a is given by:

$$a_B = a_f = a_r = a \quad (30)$$

- e) *Saturation Current I_s* : The saturation current is also similar among the three modes, and similar to R_s and a it can only be obtained from monofacial or bifacial measurements:

$$I_{sB} = I_{sf} = I_{sr} = I_s \quad (31)$$

- f) *Inhomogeneous Resistance R_h* : This resistance pertains to the localized shunt paths on the rear of the panel. It can only be determined using rear-only measurements and it is deactivated in monofacial mode representation. The bifacial inhomogeneous resistance R_{hB} is expressed as:

$$R_{hB} = R_h \frac{G_r}{G_{Br}} \quad (32)$$

Where: G_{Br} is the bifacial rear irradiance, and R_{hr} is measured using rear-only mode at an irradiance G_r . During monofacial model $G_{Br} = 0$, thereby eliminating the whole resistance-diode branch.

- g) *Ideality Factor a_h* : This ideality factor belongs to the diode that represents the unique recombination losses at the rear-side. It can be determined using rear-only measurements exclusively and deactivated in monofacial mode.

$$a_{hB} = a_{hr} \quad (33)$$

- h) *Saturation Current I_h* : This is the saturation current that represents the unique recombination losses at the rear-side. Similar to a_h It is determined using rear-only measurements exclusively and deactivated in monofacial mode. During bifacial mode of temperature T_B , I_{hB} is expressed as:

$$I_{hB} = I_{hr} \left(\frac{T_B}{T_r} \right)^3 e^{\frac{qE_g}{N_s n k} \left(\frac{1}{T_r} - \frac{1}{T_B} \right)} \quad (34)$$

The advantage of this proposed model is that it includes parameters from both the front and the rear, unlike the front-based SDM which totally disregards the unique properties of

the rear. All the while, it acknowledges the interconnected overlap between them in one bifacial entity as opposed to the parallel model which treats them as two separate bodies. On the other hand, it adds to the complexity of the modeling with 8 parameters instead of 5.

A. Results and Discussion

The previous bifacial correlations were implemented to reconstruct the bifacial I-V curves using parameters extracted from the front and the proposed rear model on one hand. On the other hand, the modified TSLLS was applied to extract the proposed model's parameters from the measured bifacial data. The extracted parameters using bifacial data and those of the proposed rear model (translated to bifacial mode according to Section. IV) are shown in Fig. 10(a)-(e). The series resistance R_s , diode's ideality factor, and saturation current are provided in Fig. 3. The parameters show good correlations. The diode's D_h ideality factor and saturation current of exhibit more deviations, but they are still in acceptable accordance with the ones extracted using bifacial curves. The reason for this discrepancy could be attributed to many factors beyond the scope of this work, including the inexactitude of the translation equations and measurements errors. Measured and reconstructed curves, obtained using the proposed model as well as the DDM ($R_h = 0$), are illustrated in Fig. 11 while the errors, sorted with descending temperature, are provided in Fig. 12. Fig. 12 highlights the superiority of the proposed model compared to DDM. The fitted curves align with the measured ones, which underscores the correlation between the accuracy of rear modeling and the overall bifacial performance prediction. However, similar to rear-side results, some deviations persist in the exponential region at lower temperatures. The MAE and RMSE, which initially ranged from 10% and 20% using the classic SDM, are reduced to $< 8\%$ using the proposed model. By contrast, the reduction in ΔP was not as significant as it was already lower than 5% using the classical SDM (Fig. 5). However, P_{max} shifted from being overestimated using the classic SDM to underestimated using the proposed model. The MAE and RMSE of the DDM are nonuniform, showing multiple spikes that exceed 10%, reaching 25% at worst, though they remain similar to the proposed model otherwise. In brief, the results confirm two major points: 1) the validity of the proposed model to account for the three modes of bifacial

Fig. 10. Extracted parameters of the proposed model: a) Photogenerated Current b) Inhomogeneous Resistance c) Parallel Resistance d) Ideality Factor e) Inhomogeneous Current.

Fig. 11. Measured vs Reconstructed Bifacial I-V Curves using DDM and the proposed bifacial model of a) July and b) March measurements

Fig. 12. RMSE, MAE, and ΔP of Bifacial IV curves reconstructed using DDM and the proposed bifacial model

operations; and 2) they differentiate and show its superiority compared to traditional DDM.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work consists of three parts. First, the electrical modeling of a PERC bifacial PV modules was extensively investigated. The results proved the shortcomings of the widely accepted SDM to model bifacial modules: 1) it exhibits large deviations that reach up to 15%; 2) the root of these errors is accentuated in the exponential region. Second, the question of rear-only modeling which seems to be ignored in the literature was also raised and an improved model tailored to the particularity of the rear structure was proposed. The results demonstrate the accuracy of the proposed model and its superiority compared to the DDM. The rear error dropped from 30% using the classical model to 12% using the proposed model. However, the error of the proposed rear model seem to correlate inversely with temperature. Deeper investigations of

this trend might be required in future works. Last, relationships between the front and the rear parameters during bifacial mode are established and the proposed model is extended to adapt to the three modes of bifacial PV. The results validate the adequacy of the proposed model, demonstrates good correlations between the parameters, and reduces the error below 8%. At the end, while the results of this study might have answered some questions, its scope remains limited and it might have opened more questions than it answered. First, the results of this work and the proposed model were validated using PERC half-cut technology. Similarly, the introduced formulas relating the front and rear parameters to the bifacial parameters are different than the few proposed in literature, which themselves differ from eachother. Future works should investigate those correlations and the extent of proposed model’s validity among other PV technologies such as HJT, TOPcon, etc, as well as in large-scale installations.

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